

STUDIES IN ELBS PERSULPHATE OXIDATION. PART II. OXIDATION OF α - AND β -NAPHTHOLS AND SOME NAPHTHOL DERIVATIVES

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α -Naphthol, 2-acetyl- α -naphthol, 1-hydroxy-2-naphthoic acid, β -naphthol, 2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid, 4'-methyl-1:2-naphtho- α -pyrone and 4'-methyl-2:1-naphtho- α -pyrone have been subjected to nuclear oxidation with potassium persulphate in alkaline solution and the corresponding *para*- or *ortho*-oxidation products obtained.

In continuation of the work described in part I (Parikh and Sethna, this *Journal*, 1950, 27, 369) on the oxidation of some coumarin derivatives, 4'-methyl-1:2-naphtho- α -pyrone was subjected to this oxidation by following the technique described in part I of opening out the α -pyrone ring, and the hitherto unknown 4-hydroxy-4'-methyl-1:2-naphtho- α -pyrone (I) derivative obtained in good yield. As the oxidation of naphthol derivatives with potassium persulphate has not been studied before and as the statement of Baker and Brown (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 2303) that this reaction was not successful with α -naphthol appeared incongruous with the above finding, it was thought worthwhile studying the application of this reaction to α - and β -naphthols and some of their derivatives. The general reaction conditions of Baker and Brown (*loc. cit.*) have been followed. It is now found that α -naphthol can be successfully oxidised and 1:4-dihydroxynaphthalene obtained. A complex product is also formed in this reaction. 1:4-Dihydroxynaphthalene has been previously prepared by a number of workers by the reduction of α -naphthaquinone (Groves, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1873, 23, 209; Plimpton, *ibid.*, 1880, 37, 635; Wolff, *Annalen*, 1913, 399, 278; Spruit, *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1947, 66, 655).

1:4-Dihydroxynaphthalene on Pechmann condensation with ethyl acetoacetate gave the same coumarin as obtained by the oxidation of 4'-methyl-1:2-naphtho- α -pyrone.

2-Acetyl- α -naphthol has been oxidised in good yield to 1:4-dihydroxy-2-acetylnaphthalene which has been recently prepared by Spruit (*loc. cit.*) by Fries reaction on 1:4-diacetoxynaphthalene. 1-Hydroxy-2-naphthoic acid has been oxidised in good yield to the known 1:4-dihydroxynaphthalene-2-carboxylic acid, previously prepared by carboxylation of 1:4-dihydroxynaphthalene (Russig, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1900, ii, 82, 30) and by the action of alkaline sodium hyposulphite on diethyl 1:4-dihydroxy-2:3-naphthalate (Homeyer and Wallingford, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 64, 800).

β -Naphthol on oxidation gave the known 1:2-dihydroxynaphthalene in a very poor yield. Baker and Brown (*loc. cit.*), who have also oxidised β -naphthol by this method, observe that the yield of the oxidation product is insignificant. 1:2-Dihydroxynaphthalene has been prepared previously by the Dakin oxidation of 1-acetyl-2-naphthol and 2-acetyl-1-naphthol (Minoru Imoto, *J. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1937, 58, 932) and by the reduction of β -naphthoquinone (Stenhouse and Groves, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1877, 31, 53; Liebermann and Jacobsen, *Annalen*, 1882, 211, 58; Paul, *Z. angew. Chem.*, 1897, 10, 24; Fieser and Hartwell, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 57, 1484).

2-Hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid has been oxidised in better yield than in the case of β -naphthol to the known 1:2-dihydroxynaphthoic acid, previously prepared by a series of reactions from 1-naphthalene-azo-2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid (Mohlau and Kriebel, *Ber.*, 1895, 28, 3089) and by the action carbon dioxide on disodium β -naphthoquinol (Russig, *loc.cit.*).

4'-Methyl-2:1-naphtho- α -pyrone has also been oxidised and a product obtained in poor yield.

The 3-position in β -naphthol is found to be very unreactive and if the 1-position is occupied, either the substitution does not take place or it takes place preferably in the 6-position (cf. Fieser and Lothrop, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 57, 1459; Bell and Hunter, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 2903). The structure of 6-hydroxy-4'-methyl-2:1-naphtho- α -pyrone (II) is therefore tentatively assigned to the above oxidation product.

It has been found in the present work that in the case of α -naphthol and its derivatives the oxidation takes place with the formation of 1:4-dihydroxynaphthalene and its derivatives in about 25% yield. In the case of β -naphthol and its derivatives, however, the yields are very poor because the oxidation has to take place in the *ortho* or the 6-position. This is in keeping with the observation made in the case of oxidation of phenols and their derivatives that in *ortho*-oxidation the yields are very poor (Baker and Brown, *loc.cit.*).

1:4-Dihydroxybenzenes and -naphthalenes are hitherto obtained from phenols and α -naphthol derivatives through a series of reactions. The smooth formation of these compounds in a single step therefore suggests its wider application in synthetic work.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Oxidation of α -Naphthol-1:4-dihydroxynaphthalene.— α -Naphthol (7.2 g.) was dissolved in sodium hydroxide solution (10 g. in 100 c.c. of water) and a saturated solution of potassium persulphate (13.5 g. in 270 c.c. of water) was added dropwise during 3 hours with mechanical stirring, at 0°. After the addition was complete the reaction mixture was kept overnight in a frijidare. It was then just acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid when some black substance (4 g.) came down. This was refluxed with rectified spirit and filtered. The filtrate on evaporation yielded a small quantity of α -naphthol, while the insoluble substance was found to be a complex product which did not melt even on a spatula. The reaction mixture was extracted with ether twice. The

ether extract on removal of the solvent yielded further quantities of α -naphthol (total yield, 1 g.) Excess of hydrochloric acid (150 c.c.) was then added and the reaction mixture heated on a boiling water-bath for half an hour. It was then allowed to cool when it deposited long needles (1.4 g.) of 1:4-dihydroxynaphthalene. The crystals were filtered and recrystallised from rectified spirit in colorless tiny needles, m.p. 192°. Russig (*loc. cit.*) gives m.p. 187° and Wolff (*loc. cit.*), m.p. 192°. Ether extract gave a further quantity (0.2 g.) of the same substance.

It is found that if the reaction mixture is not cooled properly during the addition of potassium persulphate, no 1:4-dihydroxynaphthalene is obtained but only a complex product melting at a high temperature is obtained which we have not worked up further.

Diacetyl Derivative.—1:4 Dihydroxynaphthalene was acetylated as usual with acetic anhydride and fused sodium acetate and the product obtained was crystallised from dilute alcohol in colorless plates, m.p. 127°. Korn (*Ber.*, 1884, 17, 3025) gives m.p. 128-30°; Russig (*loc. cit.*), m.p. 125°.

Oxidation of 2-Acetylnaphthol: 1:4-Dihydroxy-2-acetylnaphthalene.—2-Acetyl- α -naphthol (3.1 g.), prepared according to Witt and Braun (*Ber.*, 1914, 47, 3219), was added to sodium hydroxide solution (3.4 g. in 84 c.c. of water). As it did not form a clear solution even on heating on a steam-bath, pyridine (15 c. c.) was added to dissolve it. The oxidation was carried out as before with potassium persulphate (4.5 g. in 90 c. c. of water). On working up the reaction mixture the product (2 g.) which came down on just acidification was found to be the starting material. The product obtained during heating with excess of concentrated hydrochloric acid (50 c.c.) was crystallised from rectified spirit in tiny yellow needles (0.8 g.), m.p. 210°. Spruit (*loc. cit.*) gives m.p. 206° (closed capillary). It gave a pale green coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride.

The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, prepared as usual, was crystallised from acetic acidpyridine mixture in dark red tiny needles, m.p. 265-67° (decomp.). (Found: N, 14.2. $C_{14}H_{10}O_6N_4$ requires N, 14.6 per cent). The *diacetyl derivative*, prepared with acetic anhydride and pyridine as usual, was crystallised from rectified spirit in brown needles, m. p. 100°. Spruit (*loc. cit.*) gives m. p. 102°.

Oxidation of 1-Hydroxy-2-naphthoic Acid: 1:4-Dihydroxy-2-naphthoic Acid.—1-Hydroxy-2-naphthoic acid which was previously prepared (Eller, *Annalen*, 1869, 182, 277; Schaeffer, *ibid.*, 1869, 182, 291) by passing carbon dioxide in a mixture of α -naphthol and sodium at water-bath temperature, or by treating the dry sodium salt of α -naphthol with carbon dioxide and then heating the naphthyl carbonic acid salt in an autoclave at 120°-140° (Schmitt, *Ber.*, 1887, 20, 2699) or by passing CO_2 in a boiling solution of sodium and α -naphthol in toluene (Oddo, *Atti Accad. Lincei*, v, 10, 241) has now been prepared by the following simplified method.

α -Naphthol (15 g.) was thoroughly mixed with potassium bicarbonate (30 g.) and glycerine (30 g.) was added and the mixture heated at 120°-125° for 4 hours in an oil-bath and a steady stream of carbon dioxide passed in all the time. The solid formed was treated with water and the insoluble, unreacted α -naphthol was filtered. The carbonate solution was then acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid and the solid obtained

was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from rectified spirit in needles (7 g.), m.p. 194-95°. Eller (*loc.cit.*) gives m.p. 186-88°; Anschutz, Weber and Runkel (*Annalen*, 1906, 346, 361), m.p. 191-92°.

The above acid (3.1 g.) was dissolved in sodium hydroxide solution (3.4 g. in 34 c.c. of water) and was oxidised with potassium persulphate (4.5 g. in 90 c.c. of water). The product (1 g.), which came down on just acidification, was found to be the original acid. The product obtained after heating with excess of concentrated hydrochloric acid (50 c.c.) was crystallised from glacial acetic acid in needles (0.8 g.), m.p. 201-202°. Russig (*loc.cit.*) gives m.p. 186°; Homeyer and Wallingford (*loc.cit.*), m.p. 200°. It gives a green coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride and the solution in alcohol shows a blue fluorescence.

Monoacetyl Derivative: 1-Hydroxy-4-acetoxy-2-naphthoic Acid.—It was prepared by heating the above acid with acetic anhydride and pyridine, and crystallised from acetic acid in colorless plates, m.p. 194-95°. Russig (*loc.cit.*) gives m.p. 193°.

Oxidation of β -Naphthol: 1:2-Dihydroxynaphthalene.— β -Naphthol (7.2 g.) was dissolved in sodium hydroxide solution (10 g. in 100 c.c. of water) and oxidised as before with potassium persulphate (13.5 g. in 270 c.c. of water). The dark coloured product (4 g.) came down on just acidification from which a small quantity of β -naphthol could be extracted by boiling with petroleum ether (b.p. 60°-80°). The reaction mixture was then heated with excess of concentrated hydrochloric acid (150 c.c.). As no precipitate was obtained the reaction mixture was extracted with ether, but only a tarry mass was obtained from the ether extract. This was extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60°-80°) when tiny white needles of 1:2-dihydroxynaphthalene were obtained in very poor yield, m.p. 103°. Fieser and Hartwell (*loc.cit.*) gives m.p. 101-102°. This substance gives no characteristic colour with alcoholic ferric chloride. It has a severe corrosive action on the skin, especially in solution.

Oxidation of 2-Hydroxy-3-naphthoic Acid: 1:2-Dihydroxy-3-naphthoic Acid.—2-Hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid (4.7 g.) was dissolved in sodium hydroxide solution (5 g. in 50 c.c. of water) and oxidised as before with potassium persulphate (6.8 g. in 140 c.c. of water). The product (2.5 g.) which came down on just acidification was found to be 2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid. The product obtained after heating with excess of concentrated hydrochloric acid (50 c.c.) was crystallised from alcohol in brownish green crystals (0.8 g.), m.p. 235° (efferv.). Mixed melting point with 2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid was lowered by over 20°. Russig (*loc.cit.*) gives m.p. 215°; Mohlau and Kriebel (*loc.cit.*), m.p. 220.5°. The acid gives a green colour with alcoholic ferric chloride. The diacetyl derivative, prepared as usual, was crystallised from glacial acetic acid in white needles, m.p. 210-11°. Russig (*loc.cit.*) and Mohlau and Kriebel (*loc.cit.*) give m.p. 206-207°.

Oxidation of 4'-Methyl-1:2-naphtho- α -pyrone: 4-Hydroxy-4'-methyl-1:2-naphtho- α -pyrone (I).—4'-Methyl-1:2-naphtho- α -pyrone (2 g.) (Robertson, Sandrock and Hendry, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 2426) was dissolved in sodium hydroxide solution (2 g. in 20 c.c. of water) by heating on a boiling water-bath and oxidised with potassium persulphate (2.6 g. in 55 c.c. of water). The product (0.2 g.) which came down on just acidification was found to be the starting material. The product obtained after heating with excess

of concentrated hydrochloric acid (50 c.c.) was crystallised from dilute alcohol in yellowish tiny needles (0.8 g.), m.p. 288-89°. (Found: C, 73.8; H, 4.7. $C_{14}H_{10}O$, requires C, 74.3; H, 4.4 per cent). The product is soluble in sodium hydroxide with deep yellow colour and gives no coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride. Mixed melting point with the product obtained by the Pechmann condensation of 1:4-dihydroxynaphthalene (1 g.) (obtained by the oxidation of α -naphthol as described before) and acetoacetic ester (1.2 g.) in presence of sulphuric acid (80%, 8 c.c.) by keeping overnight was not depressed.

The *acetyl derivative*, prepared as usual, was crystallised from rectified spirit in yellowish needles, m.p. 187-88°. (Found: C, 71.2; H, 4.5. $C_{14}H_{12}O$, requires C, 71.6; H, 4.5 per cent).

Oxidation of 4'-Methyl-2:1-naphtho- α -pyrone : 6-Hydroxy-4'-methyl-2:1-naphtho- α -pyrone (II).—4'-Methyl 2:1-naphtho- α -pyrone (4 g.) (Murti, Rao and Seshadri, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1937, **6A**, 321) was dissolved in sodium hydroxide (4 g. in 40 c.c. of water) and oxidised with potassium persulphate (5.2 g. in 100 c.c. of water). The product (1.5 g.) which came down on just acidification was found to be the starting material. The product which separated during heating with excess of concentrated hydrochloric acid (100 c.c.) was crystallised from dilute alcohol in yellow needles (0.2 g.), m.p. 285-86°. (Found: C, 74.2; H, 4.5. $C_{14}H_{10}O$, requires C, 74.3; H, 4.4 per cent). The product is sparingly soluble in sodium hydroxide and gives no coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride.

The *acetyl derivative*, prepared as usual, was crystallised from rectified spirit in tiny crystals, m.p. 190-91°. (Found: C, 71.4; H, 4.2. $C_{14}H_{12}O$, requires C, 71.6; H, 4.5 per cent).

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Received August 10, 1950.